

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D8.5

Participant recruitment, Pre-existing RWD access, Prospective RWD acquisition and secure storage -v3

March 2023

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

www.mes-cobrad.eu

PREFACE

1

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

2

It brings together internationally recognized experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalized care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.

3

It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximize project impact.

The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
UU	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
RMC-C&E	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
KCL	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
EVOLUTION	MICHOPOULOS I. & CH. G.P.	EL
UE	University of Edinburgh	UK
CEL	CyberEthics Lab	IT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY EXPERT SYSTEM FOR THE ASSESSMENT & MANAGEMENT OF COMPLEX BRAIN DISORDERS

GA#: 965422 **Start Date:** 01/04/2021
Topic: SC1-DTH-12-2020 **Duration:** 36 months
Type of Action: RIA **Coordinator:** NTUA

Deliverable Number	D8.5
Deliverable Title	Participant recruitment, Pre-existing RWD access, Prospective RWD acquisition and secure storage –v1
Work Package Number	WP8
Task Number	T8.1, T8.2, T8.3
Date of Delivery	31/03/2023
Dissemination Level	Public
Work Package Leader	IR-HSCSP
Lead Beneficiary	IR-HSCSP
Authors	IR-HSCSP, NIA, KCL, CHS-RMC, UU
Contributors	NIA, KCL, CHS-RMC, UU
Reviewers	CHS-RMC, NTUA

Disclaimer

The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. Neither the EASME nor the European Commission is responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Copyright Message

This report, if not confidential, is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0); a copy is available here: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>. You are free to share (copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format) and adapt (remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially) under the following terms: (i) attribution (you must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made; you may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use); (ii) no additional restrictions (you may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits).

Document History

Version	Date	Author (Partner)	Remarks/Changes
0.10	14/03/2023	Javier Arranz (IR-HSCSP), Elissaios Karageorgiou (NIA), Antonio Valentin (KCL), Ophir Keret (CHS-RMC), Luiz Eduardo Mateus Brandao (UU)	Content/Creation
0.20	20/03/2023	CHS-RMC	Review 1
0.30	24/03/2023	George Doukas (NTUA), Loukas Ilias (NTUA)	Review 2
0.40	27/03/2023	Javier Arranz (IR-HSCSP)	Merge review/ final draft
0.50	30/03/2023	Michael Kontoulis (NTUA)	Quality Control
1.00	31/03/2023	Christos Ntanos (NTUA)	Final Version to be Submitted

Table of Contents

LIST OF TABLES	7
List Of Abbreviations.....	8
1 Introduction.....	9
2 Working groups.....	10
2.1 King’s College London/King’s College Hospital (KCL).....	10
2.1.1 Participant enrolment procedure.....	10
2.1.2 Participant recruitment summary.....	10
2.1.3 Retrospective RWD data report.....	10
2.1.4 Recruitment report	10
2.1.5 Data storage.....	11
2.2 Neurological Institute of Athens (NIA).....	11
2.2.1 Participant enrolment procedure.....	11
2.2.2 Participant recruitment summary.....	11
2.2.3 Retrospective RWD data report.....	11
2.2.4 Recruitment report	11
2.2.5 Data storage.....	11
2.3 Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive and Epilepsy Clinics (RMC-RABIN)	12
2.3.1 Participant enrolment procedure.....	12
2.3.2 Participant recruitment summary.....	12
2.3.3 Retrospective RWD data report.....	12
2.3.4 Recruitment report	12
2.3.5 Data storage.....	13
2.4 Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l’Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau (HSCSP-IR)..	13
2.4.1 Participant enrolment procedure.....	13
2.4.2 Participant recruitment summary.....	13
2.4.3 Retrospective RWD data report.....	13
2.4.4 Recruitment report	13
2.4.5 Data storage.....	14
3 SECURE DATA SHARING.....	14
4 SUMMARY REPORT	15

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 . Summary of participant recruitments. Retro = retrospective, Prosp = prospective, N/A = Non applicable, CSH = Clinical Symptoms History, PE = Physical Examination, NPT = Neuropsychological Assessment, MRI = Magnetic Resonance Imaging, CSF = Cerebrospinal Fluid.....15

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
EEG	Electroencephalogram
IRB	Institutional Review Board
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
NPT	Neuropsychological testing
PSG	Polysomnography
RWD	Real World data

1 INTRODUCTION

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) project integrates a group of professionals with inter-expertise and where a wide number of different fields of research interact. Four centres from the collaborative effort, have agreed to incorporate participant data, ranging from clinical and NPT data to MRI and biosamples. During the project, five different reports will summarize the status of participant enrolment and secure data upload into the platform. Such reports will, internally, help to identify recruitment progress and address issues in RWD acquisition and secure sharing, and solutions to troubleshoot them. This is report number 3.

Each centre will detail the current status of retrospective and prospective RWD available for platform inclusion, and report on the current status of participant recruitment and data storage. Since we have started to include data in the edge module, a section about secure data sharing has been included.

The last section of this delivery summarizes, in simplified tables, the general status of participant recruitment.

2 WORKING GROUPS

2.1 KING'S COLLEGE LONDON/KING'S COLLEGE HOSPITAL (KCL)

2.1.1 PARTICIPANT ENROLMENT PROCEDURE

The participant recruitment process is the same as previously described (D8.4). Briefly, KCL will recruit participants for the MES-CoBraD project through King's College Hospital (KCH). The Department of Neurophysiology at KCH is the biggest neurophysiology department in England and supports all types of neurophysiology testing, providing also presurgical assessment for epilepsy surgery through inpatient video-EEG recordings at the Epilepsy Monitoring Unit and Home Video-EEG Telemetry for the diagnosis of epilepsy and non-epileptic paroxysmal events. The participants will be recruited from epilepsy patients electively admitted at the Epilepsy Monitoring Unit for EEG telemetry recording, as part of their presurgical evaluation or for other indications of monitoring their seizure activity. The candidates (based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria) will be spotted from the admissions' schedule and will receive a patient information sheet with detailed information about MES-CoBraD project included in the confirmation letter for their admission. Upon admission, a member of the clinical team will inform the patient about the project and answer any questions, in order to obtain informed consent. The patient then will have to provide the decision on taking or not part after 24 hours. The patients consenting to participate will be tested according to the MES-CoBraD pilot protocol, modified to fit the clinical requirements of the admission.

Retrospective data is being collected from a curated list of patients who had video-EEG telemetry and/or Polysomnography at the department of Neurophysiology of KCH in the past, as part of epilepsy or possible sleep disorder evaluation. The use of retrospective has already been approved by the KCH Caldicott Guardian given the data are fully anonymized and consent form is not required.

2.1.2 PARTICIPANT RECRUITMENT SUMMARY

KCL have started to collect prospective data after Integrated Research Application System (IRAS) approval in October 2022. In the meantime, KCL have obtained and implemented the RedCap platform to collect clinical and NPT data. Part of the questionnaires have already been uploaded onto the platform, whereas the missing test/scales are being created for RedCap. KCL received the actigraphs hardware the 28/02/2022. KCL will prepare a pilot study to evaluate the pipeline to send/receive the actigraphs, and check quality and export of data collected. Overall, the total number of participants with completed minimal required RWD (≥ 4 RWD) is of 2 participants.

2.1.3 RETROSPECTIVE RWD DATA REPORT

KCL have identified 29 potential cases of retrospective data to be included in the MES-CoBraD project. This set of participants already have PSG and/or video EEG. Moreover, KCL will export clinical, NPT and (when available) MRI data to upload into the platform. Retrospective data will be fully anonymized, including defacing MRI. An excel file, with all the important information from the retrospective data, will be created in order to upload the data from a tabular file.

2.1.4 RECRUITMENT REPORT

KCL have recruited 2 prospective patients, since IRAS approval in mid-October. KCL expects to recruit 10 prospective cases by the next report.

2.1.5 DATA STORAGE

Data is stored at King's Collage Hospital Server. Non-anonymized raw data will be kept at King's College Hospital server, protected by secure password. Data will be anonymized (including MRI defacing) and transferred to an encrypted hard disk (already approved by KCH). Questionnaires and/or clinical data acquired using paper, will be digitalized and uploaded into the RedCap platform. Physical copies will be securely stored at a secured office located at KCH.

2.2 NEUROLOGICAL INSTITUTE OF ATHENS (NIA)

2.2.1 PARTICIPANT ENROLMENT PROCEDURE

The participant recruitment process is the same as previously described (D8.4). Briefly, NIA enrolment has different approaches. Most participants enrol directly through clinic, as outlined in the Grant Agreement. A subset of participants reaches out to participate purely on a research basis, after being informed of the study through dissemination and outreach activities, such as information through our website, flyers, presentations to the public, social networks, and traditional media (e.g., TV interviews on the project). Finally, several participants are referred to the NIA through the NIA network of professional colleagues.

All participants sign an informed consent, as approved by the NIA IRB, after having the study explained to them, and prior to contributing any data. Historical anonymized and depersonalized data are accessible for analysis and platform upload as approved by the NIA IRB.

2.2.2 PARTICIPANT RECRUITMENT SUMMARY

NIA obtained IRB approval on 22nd of Sept 2021 to collect prospective data in relation to the MES-CoBraD project. RWD, as per the grant agreement, are collected through the MES-CoBraD Protocol. Both standard of care RWD and research RWD are contributed by patients after informed consent. Patients are not charged for any additional workup (e.g., plasma acquisition) that is not part of their standard clinical care, as per grant agreement. Recruitment status is noted in the tables below.

2.2.3 RETROSPECTIVE RWD DATA REPORT

NIA has obtained IRB approval to include retrospective data into the MES-CoBraD platform. A total of 84 participants could be included and data are under quality control for accuracy and compliance with study protocols.

2.2.4 RECRUITMENT REPORT

NIA has prospectively recruited a total of 136 participants from 22nd Sept 2021 until March 13th 2023. Participants are at varied stages of providing data and having their paper-form data reviewed for quality and uploaded to the NIA intranet. This information is dynamically changing daily. See tables below on current status as of March 13, 2023.

2.2.5 DATA STORAGE

NIA stores all scanned paper documents and RWD from MRI, PSG, EEG and actigraphs in a secure GDPR

compliant database protected with a secured-password and controlled access.

2.3 CLALIT HEALTH SERVICES- RABIN MEDICAL CENTER COGNITIVE AND EPILEPSY CLINICS (RMC-RABIN)

2.3.1 PARTICIPANT ENROLMENT PROCEDURE

The participant recruitment process is the same as previously described (D8.4). Briefly, for pilot data recruitment, RMC has prepared a flier (authorized by IRB), which is distributed by the CHS (parent organization) and the Israeli Alzheimer Patient association. Moreover, participants can self-refer to the neurological clinic and undergo a pre-screening visit to make sure they are compatible to be included in the MES-CoBraD project.

For retrospective data, RMC will use a curated list of already screened participants from the memory and epilepsy clinic. Consent is waived (by the IRB) in retrospective data.

2.3.2 PARTICIPANT RECRUITMENT SUMMARY

RMC site have IRB approval to collect prospective data in relation to the MES-CoBraD project. Clinical and NPT data is collected in paper or via RedCap platform. Forms are guided, for self-administration, via two research coordinators. NPT and cognitive tests are assessed by two neuropsychologists, with previous expertise in CoBraD. Assessment of genetic and clinical family history, and physical examination, is performed by a neurologist with advance training in epilepsy and/or cognitive decline. EEG and PSG recordings are connected at RMC and perform the test there and at home. Participants are connected to long term EEG and PSG at the center during the afternoon, they sleep at home, and disconnected the next morning at the center. Two trained technicians assure the quality of the recordings post disconnection of the equipment. Epilepsy specialists summarize the EEG and PSG findings. All participants that are included for PSG data recording, receive an actigraphy 7 +/- days before the acquisition. The blood draw is performed twice, before and after sleep recording with EGG/PSG. MRI data is acquired at Tel Aviv University research grade MRI. The RedCap institution platform is used for data entry of all questionnaires, consensus, genetic history, cognitive testing and background diagnosis, in addition to sleep diary information. Overall, the total number of participants with completed minimal required RWD (≥ 4 RWD), is 53 participants.

2.3.3 RETROSPECTIVE RWD DATA REPORT

RMC-RABIN do have IRB approval to collect, and include into the MES-CoBraD platform, retrospective data. IRB has been recently approved, and retrospective data will be upload into the platform in the forthcoming months.

2.3.4 RECRUITMENT REPORT

Reported number of participants are accounted between 17th February of 2022 and 13th March of 2023. A total number of 61 participants were recruited.

2.3.5 DATA STORAGE

All questionnaire data is stored on paper (when needed) and RedCap. EEG, PSG and MRI data is exported in raw data and stored on an external drive, docked and protected using a secure password.

2.4 FUNDACIÓ PRIVADA INSTITUT DE RECERCA DE L'HOSPITAL DE LA SANTA CREU I SANT PAU (HSCSP-IR)

2.4.1 PARTICIPANT ENROLMENT PROCEDURE

The participant recruitment process is the same as previously described (D8.4). HSCSP-IR is a tertiary hospital, where subjects with neurological complains, that live in a urban region close by the hospital, will attend to a neurological evaluation. The HSCSP-IR Memory Unit is focused on cognitive complains, and as a result, the enrolled participants for the MES-CoBraD project will have a cognitive alteration profile. During the routine visit, participants will be asked to sign a consent that their data can be included in the MES-CoBraD study and asked to perform extra RWD acquisition. Moreover, the HSCSP-IR Memory Unit collaborate with the Fundacio Catalana de Sindrome de Down, performing neurological evaluations in adults with Down Syndrome from across the Catalonia region. Thus, a subset of the included participants from the MES-CoBraD will be adults with Down Syndrome. In addition, a subset of healthy controls will be included from the SPIN cohort.

2.4.2 PARTICIPANT RECRUITMENT SUMMARY

IRB proposal has been approved. HSCSP-IR has already started collecting data in relation to the MES-CoBraD project. HSCSP-IR have installed the latest RedCap software, and have digitalized (and uploaded) most of the questionnaires into the RedCap. NPT will be acquired by one neuropsychologist trained in CoBraD. Actigraphs will be send to participants one week previous to PSG acquisition. PSG/EEG will be supervised by a specialized technician and a specialized neurology will evaluate its quality and report important findings. Blood drawing will be performed during the sleep visit and preprocessed immediately to be stored in -80 degree freezers. Extra sleep-related questionnaires will perform pre-post PSG acquisition. MRI data will be acquired at the Hospital Clinic de Barcelona, as close in time as possible to the acquisition of clinical and neurophysiological data. MRI images will be inspected by a neuroradiologist to assess image quality and identify clinically relevant findings. The RedCap institution platform is ready to upload all questionnaires, consensus, genetic history, cognitive testing and background diagnosis, and will integrate the corresponding information of sleep tests.

2.4.3 RETROSPECTIVE RWD DATA REPORT

HSCSP-IR is not expecting to include retrospective data.

2.4.4 RECRUITMENT REPORT

HSCSP-IR have recruited 72 prospective patients. HSCSP-IR expect to recruit at least 50 patients more for the next report, most of them with ≥ 4 RWD categories. Overall, the total number of participants with completed minimal required RWD (≥ 4 RWD), is of 45 participants.

2.4.5 DATA STORAGE

Collected data (NPT and clinical scales) are stored in an internal database, restricted to access only within the hospital's network. MRI, EEG/PSG and actigraphs data will be exported and securely stored in a computational cluster, only accessible from within hospital's network, using user and password credentials. Paper reports will be stored in a secure office within the Hospital. Biosamples will be stored in adequate freezers, with restricted access only granted to key personnel of the project.

SECURE DATA SHARING

As described previously, retro- and prospective data is being collected and stored locally by each partner. This ensures that the data remains secure and under the control of the respective clinical site. To ensure that personal data is removed from the collected data before ingestion in the cloud counterpart of the MES-CoBraD platform, technical consortium partners have already developed and implemented an edge module for all the supported RWD types anonymisation, including questionnaires, magnetic resonance imaging, and actigraphy. Once the data is anonymized, it is ingested in the data lake that is built and maintained by the technical consortium partners. The common database for the MES-CoBraD platform follows a distinctive architecture as detailed in deliverable D5.2, ensuring the security and privacy of the collected data. Apart from blood samples, which are being sent to Uppsala University for further analysis, no other RWD is being shared between partners. However, as the project moves forward, we anticipate that the data sharing among organizations will intensify and will be done through the MES-CoBraD platform. No questions or demands arose regarding the security measures implemented for data sharing in the previous months (i.e. blood samples). We will continue to monitor and enhance our data sharing practices ensuring the highest level of security.

4 SUMMARY REPORT

The table (Table 1) summarize the status of the participant recruitment (retrospective and prospective) and data storage status for each of the clinical partners that will contribute with RWD into the MES-CoBraD platform.

Table 1 . Summary of participant recruitments. Retro = retrospective, Prosp = prospective, N/A = Non applicable, CSH = Clinical Symptoms History, PE = Physical Examination, NPT = Neuropsychological Assessment, MRI = Magnetic Resonance Imaging, CSF = Cerebrospinal Fluid

[Prospective data report \(30/03/23\)](#)

CENTER	RWD	NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS	%
KCL	CSH	0	0
	PE	0	0
	NPT	0	0
	MRI	0	0
	CSF	0	0
	Blood	0	0
	PSG/EEG	0	0
	Actigraphy	0	0
	Hair	0	0
	Total	0	0
	RWD \geq 4	0	0
NIA	CSH	117	86%
	PE	116	85%
	NPT	119	88%
	MRI	49	36%
	CSF	0	0%
	Blood	62	46%
	PSG/EEG	100	74%
	Actigraphy	129	95%
	Hair	67	49%
	Total	136	100%
	RWD \geq 4	103	76%
RMC	CSH	54	89%
	PE	37	61%
	NPT	59	97%
	MRI	41	67%

CENTER	RWD	NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS	%
	CSF	1	2%
	Blood	55	90%
	PSG/EEG	51	84%
	Actigraphy	42	69%
	Hair	40	66%
	Total	61	100%
	RWD≥4	53	87%
IR-HSCSP	CSH	68	94%
	PE	55	76%
	NPT	42	58%
	MRI	18	25%
	CSF	39	54%
	Blood	18	25%
	PSG/EEG	62	86%
	Actigraphy	18	25%
	Hair	17	24%
	Total	72	100%
	RWD≥4	45	63%

[Retrospective data Report 2 \(30/03/2023\)](#)

CENTER	RWD	TOTAL
KCL	CSH	29
	PE	0
	NPT	3
	MRI	12
	CSF	0
	Blood	0
	PSG/EEG	24
	Actigraphy	0
	Hair	0
	CSH	81

CENTER	RWD	TOTAL
NIA	PE	36
	NPT	81
	MRI	24
	CSF	0
	Blood	3
	PSG/EEG	0
	Actigraphy	80
	Hair	2
	<hr/>	
RMC	CSH	0
	PE	0
	NPT	0
	MRI	0
	CSF	0
	Blood	0
	PSG/EEG	0
	Actigraphy	0
	Hair	0
<hr/>		
IR-HSCSP	Not including	